

**PRINCIPALS' SELF-CONFIDENCE AND PERSEVERANCE AND
THEIR ADMINISTRATIVE TASK PERFORMANCE IN PUBLIC
SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN EKET SENATORIAL DISTRICT OF
AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA**

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Abstract

The study examined principals' self-confidence and perseverance and their administrative task performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom South (Eket), Senatorial District of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Two research questions and two corresponding null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. A correlational research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study consisted of 63 school principals and all the 1702 teachers of the public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom South (Eket) Senatorial District. The sample for this study was 340 teachers from the seven LECs selected through the proportional sampling technique which forms 20% of the total number of teachers in each of the LECs. Two research instruments tagged "Principals' Self-confidence and Perseverance Questionnaire" (PSPQ) and Principals' Administrative Task Performance Questionnaire (PATPQ)" were used for data collection. The questionnaires were administered and the data generated in this study were analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis (PPMC). All the research questions and hypotheses were tested at a .05 level of significance. The results of the study showed that leadership traits of self-confidence and perseverance of school principals significantly relate to their administrative task performance in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District (Eket Senatorial District) of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. Based on the findings of this work, it was recommended that

principals of schools should be confident in themselves at all times and that they should always persevere in the face of difficulties in order to attain the goals for which the schools were established.

Keywords: Self Confidence, Perseverance, Secondary Schools, Self-Efficiency.

1 Introduction

Principals of the Nigerian secondary schools are the heads and are saddled with the responsibility of ensuring that all the activities of the schools are carried out effectively and efficiently with the aim of attaining the goals for which these schools are established. It is important to state that the administration and management of the school system to a great extent can make or mar the achievement of the set objectives of the school.

Principals of the Nigerian secondary schools require some very unique traits or qualities as the case may be, to be able to run the affairs of the schools successfully, especially, considering the fact that most Nigerian public secondary schools are without the required facilities and personnel for productivity. Moreover, the policy of free and compulsory education at this level in Akwa Ibom State also militates against the effective administration of the schools.

Ames and Flynn (2007) categorized the traits/ qualities required of a school principal into intelligence, assertiveness (confidence), charisma, and conscientiousness. Likewise, Sharma (2011) identified the leadership traits (qualities) of a school principal to include communication skills, comfort, empathy, decision-making skill, influence, self-management, time management skills and commitment. To Lunenburg and Orstein (2018), other leadership traits or qualities that can enhance effective administrative task performance of school principals are relationships and emotional stability.

For the purpose of this study, self-confidence and perseverance will be considered as the leadership traits vis-à-vis the administrative effectiveness of principals in public secondary schools in Eket Senatorial District of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

The administration of public secondary schools in Nigeria and in Akwa Ibom state to be specific has become very complex due to an increase in student enrolment as a result of the policy of free and compulsory education, the advent of modern technology and the expanded curriculum (Akpan & Archibong, 2012). To make the situation worrisome, facilities in the public secondary schools are in a state of decay with little or no hope for their replacement. Likewise, principals tend to contribute to the problem especially when they do not have the capacity and the skills required to maintain the few facilities that the government manages to provide. Sometimes, the principals are accused of negligence, laziness, permissiveness, lack of dedication, and zeal to work (Umosen and Ogon 2020). It is therefore not wrong to say that lack of leadership traits required of a school principal for the effective administration of our schools is tantamount to poor performance of teachers who are at the centre of the teaching and learning process and by extension, the poor academic performance of students. Once teachers fail in their duties and students become unserious and disobedient, it means the entire school system is in a state of collapse. The results of The West African Examination Council and those of the National Examination Council of recent times are obvious proof of the fact that school principals are not administering our secondary schools effectively. It is against this background that this study investigates the influence of emotional intelligence and integrity on principals' administrative effectiveness in public secondary schools in Eket senatorial district of Akwa Ibom State.

Purpose of the Study

The specific objectives of the study are to find out how:

1. Principals' self-confidence relates to their administrative task performance in public secondary schools in Eket Senatorial District of Akwa Ibom state.
2. Principals' perseverance relates to their administrative task performance in public secondary schools in Eket Senatorial District of Akwa Ibom state.

Research Questions

The following are the research questions to guide this study.

1. How does principals' self-confidence relate to their administrative task

performance?

2. What is the relationship between principals' perseverance and their administrative task performance?

Research Hypotheses

Two null hypotheses that were formulated to guide the study are:

HO1. There is no significant relationship between principals' self-confidence and their administrative task performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District (Eket Senatorial District) of Akwa Ibom State.

HO1. There is no significant relationship between principals' perseverance and their administrative task performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District (Eket Senatorial District) of Akwa Ibom State.

2 Literature Review

The Self-Efficacy Theory by Albert Bandura (1986) was considered relevant to this study. The self-efficacy theory holds is that people are likely to engage in activities to the extent that they perceive themselves to be competent. Self-Efficacy Theory of Bandura follows the principle that people are likely to engage in activities to the extent that they perceive themselves to be competent at those activities. Self-efficacy is the belief in one's effectiveness in performing specific tasks. Albert Bandura's theory of self-efficacy has important implications for [motivation](#). In order of strength; people who regard themselves as highly efficacious act, think, and feel differently from those who perceive themselves as inefficacious. They produce their future, rather than simply foretell it.

The Self- Efficacy theory is premised on four major sources namely:

1. Performance Accomplishments.
2. Vicarious Experience.
3. Social Persuasion.
4. Physiological and Emotional States.

Performance Accomplishments: Personal assessment information is based on an individual's accomplishments. Previous successes raise mastery

expectations, while repeated failures lower them.

Vicarious Experience: Gained by observing others perform activities successfully. This is often referred to as modeling, and it can generate expectations in observers that they can improve their performance by learning from what they have observed.

Social Persuasion: Activities where people are led, through suggestion, into believing that they can cope successfully with specific tasks. Coaching and giving evaluative feedback on performance are common types of social persuasion.

Physiological and Emotional States: The individual's physiological or emotional states influence self-efficacy judgments concerning specific tasks. Emotional reactions to such tasks (e.g., anxiety) can lead to negative judgments of one's ability to complete the tasks.

Concept of Administrative Effectiveness Administration is a social process concerned with identifying, maintaining, motivating, controlling and unifying formally and informally organized human and material resources within an integrated system designed specifically to achieve predetermined objectives. Administration has to do with getting things done with the accomplishment of defined objectives (Teddy, 2004). From a broader perspective, administration could be seen as an integral part of any organization. It is crucial for maintaining and expanding the relevance, effectiveness and productivity of complex institutions. Such as Government Department, Prisons, School Systems, Universities among others (Austin, 2009). For example, the survival of all the organizations, like the schools and other institutions is dependent largely on the quality of administrative services available.

Administration, therefore, influences the results to be achieved, the direction to be pursued, and the priorities to be recognized within the organization. Administration, according to Enaohwo and Eferakeya (2009) can be defined as the process by which goals are achieved through collective and cooperative human effort in a suitable environment. This definition specifies four important points: First, administration is a process, which involves the manipulation of certain operations. Second, administration is goal-oriented.

Thirdly, a collective and cooperative human effort is required in administration, and fourthly, a suitable environment, where participants can maximize performance.

It is pertinent to relate administration in the context of education or school organizations. To be able to do that, education administration can be defined as a means of achieving the goals of education through effective and efficient manipulation of available inputs.

Aderounmu and Ehametalor (2005) defined school administration as "essentially a service, activity or tool, through which the fundamental objectives of the educational process may be more fully and efficiently realized". Educational Administration is therefore concerned with the utilization of adequate resources and the harmonization of relationships and interactions in a suitable environment, in order to foster the attainment of the goals of teaching and learning. Educational Administration involves prudent management of resources and a high degree of accountability on the part of organizational members. Educational administration broadly means running educational institutions, which involves guidance, leadership, and controlling of the efforts of individuals in the achievement of the goals of the institution (Ayanniyi, 2000).

Educational Administration also involves management of resources; human, material, and evaluation or appraising of the result of educational efforts. Having explained the concept of educational administration, it will also be wise to briefly explain school administration.

Okereke (2008) stated that school administration involves managing, administering the curriculum and teaching, disciplining, assessment, evaluation, resource allocation, costing and forward planning. The main aim of school administration is to develop an organizational structure, plan and execute an overall strategy for the content and delivery of instruction, maintain the school facilities and maintain liaison with communities, private groups and individuals to whom the school is accountable. (Akpan, 2001).

According to Onoyase (2007), the administrative tasks expected of the school administrator are:

- i. Provision of instructional academic leadership
- ii. Responsibility to staff
- iii. Responsibility to students
- iv. Managing the school's financial and physical resources
- v. Managing the school-community relations
- vi. Keeping of school records. In addition, school administration involves the following:

i. **Planning:** The school administrators undertake planning in the process of managing the school by assigning teachers to teach various subjects, preparing of time table, and assigning teachers to various post.

ii. **Organization:** the organization of the school activities by the principal is crucial in order to minimize conflict in the performance of tasks by members of staff. iii. **Directing:** The school administrator directs the activities of the school by providing good leadership to both members of staff and students. It is significant for school administrators to provide good leadership in order to achieve the goals and objectives of the school. iv. **Budgeting:** The school administrator prepares the annual estimated budgets showing the revenue and expenditure of the school every year. The school administrator indicates in the annual estimate the programs that will be implemented and the objectives of such programs. v. **Evaluation:** The evaluation of members of academic staff, non-academic staff and students is an important administrative function of the school administrator. The school administrator needs to be very objective in the evaluation of members of staff since it has great consequences on the promotion of members of staff. vi. **Coordination:** The school administrator also needs to coordinate the activities of the school in such a way that all activities in the school are related to one another. The school administrator should ensure that all the members of staff work together as a team.

Sharma (2011) identified the leadership traits (qualities) of a school principal to include communication skills, comfort, empathy, decision-making skill, influence, self-management, time management skills and commitment.

Ames and Flynn (2007) categorized these qualities into intelligence, assertiveness (confidence), charisma, and conscientiousness. According to them, intelligence has to do with the ability of a leader to be creative in solving interpersonal and work-related problems, being quick in assessing situations

and finding solutions. Conscientiousness is the ability to exhibit dedication, steadfastness and willingness to complete work in an efficiently, timely and meticulous way. Charisma on the other hand deals with the ability to motivate others to become enthusiastic about pursuing the goals of the group and the leader acting as a role model. Assertiveness refers to the ability to persist in displaying and defending one's ideas and interests in an unwavering manner and without ambivalence.

Other leadership traits or qualities that can enhance effective administrative task performance of school principals are relationships and emotional stability (Lunenburg & Orstein 2008). Relationship deals with the ability to be sociable, sympathetic, cooperative, good-natured, warm and approachable. While emotional stability refers to the capacity for composure, self-confidence and self-awareness.

According to Northouse (2013), the five traits that are central to leadership are integrity, intelligence, sociability, determination, and self-confidence.

Aghenta and Omeregic (2006), posit that the school leader (principal) provides the formal leadership and whose behaviour determines the extent to which teachers see the school as a desirable place in which to work. This suggests that the principal's leadership traits determine the organizational climate of the school and the level of teachers' commitment. Similarly, the leadership traits of the principal determine his effectiveness in the discharge of her administrative tasks. In other words, the principal effectiveness in administrative task performance is a function of his leadership traits. His leadership competence would enable him to induce the teachers and other members of staff not only to participate in school administration but also to commit themselves to the life of the school.

Effectiveness means to bring about or to accomplish; thus before action, an institution or an individual is regarded as effective, there must be an accomplishment. An organization therefore may be termed effective if it accomplishes specific goals. Consequently, administrative effectiveness is the positive response to administrative efforts and actions with the intention to accomplish stated goals. These include administrative performance in decision making, a delegation of duties and setting of examples. Supporting this

definition is McCrimmon (2007)'s findings that effective administration entails efficiency, getting things done with the least cost. Administrative effectiveness in organizations follows some principles; not just about getting results, the "how" is also critical as it entails efficiency which means reaching a destination with minimal cost. An effective administrator is an asset to an organization or institution providing the link between organizations' various parts and ensuring the smooth communication and transmission of information from one part to the other.

Jenkins (2010) posited that the work of school administrators is complex and demanding; they should know and understand their schools and communities, exert leadership to achieve positive educational outcomes and continue to develop and grow in their professional expertise.

3 Methodology

Population of the Study

The population of the study consisted of 63 principals and all the 1702 teachers of the public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District (Eket Senatorial District).

In this research, teachers were used to examine principals' leadership traits as well as their administrative effectiveness. The choice of the respondents was informed by the fact that the teachers are under the leadership of the school principals and are in the best position to provide information on their leadership traits and how such traits relate to their administrative effectiveness in the public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District (Eket Senatorial District).

Sample and Sampling Technique

The sample for this study was 340 teachers from the seven Local Education Committees (LEC) comprising 63 public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District (Eket Senatorial District) of Akwa Ibom State. The sample was selected using the proportional sampling technique. 20% of the total number of teachers in each of the Local Education Committees (LEC) were selected as a sample. Based on this technique, seventy-eight (78) teachers

were sampled from Eket Local Education Committee (LEC), eighty-one teachers from Mkpato Enin Local Education Committee (LEC), thirty-five (35) teachers from Ikot Abasi Local Education Committee (LEC), forty-seven (47) teachers from Onna Local Education Committee (LEC), thirty-eight (38) teachers from Oron Local Education Committee (LEC), twenty-one (21) teachers from Mbo Local Education Committee (LEC) and forty (40) teachers from Okobo Local Education Committee (LEC).

Instrumentation

The study was carried out using a four-point scale questionnaire. The instruments tagged “Principals’ Self-confidence and Perseverance Questionnaire” (PSPQ) and Principals’ Administrative Task Performance Questionnaire (PATPQ) were developed by the researcher. The questionnaires elicited information on principals’ leadership traits of self-confidence and perseverance and their administrative task performance from the respondents (teachers).

Method of Data Analysis

The data generated in this study were analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis (PPMC). All the hypotheses were tested at a .05 level of significance.

Decision Rule

In answering the research questions and testing the hypotheses, if the calculated r-value is greater than the critical r-value, the null hypotheses were rejected. On the contrary, if the calculated r-value is less than the critical r-value the null hypotheses were retained.

4 RESULT

Research Question One:

How does principals’ self-confidence relate to their administrative task performance in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District of Akwa Ibom State?

To answer this research question Pearson Product Moment Correlation was employed, and the data obtained are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: The Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis for the relationship between leadership trait of self-confidence and principals’ administrative task performance.

Variables	ΣX	ΣX^2	ΣXY	r.cal
	ΣY	ΣY^2		
Self Confidence(x)	5702	98528	282481	
.711				
Principals’ Admin. task performance (y)	16500	816282		

Entries in Table 1 reveal the relationship between self-confidence and principals’ administrative task performance. The result shows that the calculated r-value of .711 is very strong. This means that there is a high positive relationship between self-confidence and principals’ administrative task performance in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District (Eket Senatorial District) of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Research Question Two:

How does principals’ perseverance relate to their administrative task performance in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District of Akwa Ibom State?

To answer this research question Pearson Product Moment Correlation was employed, and the data obtained are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: The Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis for the relationship between leadership trait of perseverance and principals’ administrative task performance.

Variables	ΣX	ΣX^2	ΣXY	r.cal
	ΣY	ΣY^2		
Perseverance(x)	5746	99902	284707	
.771				
Principals’ Admin. task performance (y)	16500	816282		

Entries in Table 2 reveal the relationship between perseverance and principals’ administrative task performance. The result shows that the calculated r-value

of .771 is very strong. This means that there is a high positive relationship between perseverance and principals’ administrative task performance in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District (Eket Senatorial District) of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Testing of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One:

There is no significant relationship between principals’ self-confidence and their administrative task performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District (Eket Senatorial District) of Akwa Ibom State.

Table 3: The Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis for the relationship between Self-confidence and principals’ administrative task performance.

Variables	N	ΣX	ΣX^2	ΣXY	r.cal	r.crit
df						
sig		ΣY	ΣY^2			
Self-confidence(x)	336	5702	98528	282481	.711	0.095
sig						334
Principals’ admin task performance (y)	336	16500	816282			

Predictor: Principals’ Self-Confidence; dependent variable: Principals’ administrative effectiveness *Significant at .05 level; N = 336; critical-r 0.095

Table 3 shows that the calculated r-value of .711 is greater than the critical r–value of 0.095 at 0.05 significance level with 1 and 334 degrees of freedom. The result is significant; therefore, the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between principals’ self-confidence and their administrative task performance is rejected in favour of the alternative one. The result means that, there is a significant relationship between principals’ self-confidence and their administrative task performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District (Eket Senatorial District) of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Hypothesis Two:

There is no significant relationship between principals’ perseverance and their administrative task performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District (Eket Senatorial District) of Akwa Ibom State.

Table 4: The Pearson Product Moment Correlation analysis for the relationship between perseverance and principals’ administrative task performance.

Variables	N	ΣX	ΣX^2	ΣXY	r.cal	r.crit
df						
sig		ΣY	ΣY^2			
Perseverance(x)	336	5746	99902	284707	.771	0.095
334						
Principals’ admin task performance (y)	336	16500	816282			

Predictor: Principals’ Perseverance; dependent variable: Principals’ administrative task performance *Significant at .05 level; N = 336; critical-r 0.095

Table 4 shows that the calculated r-value of .771 is greater than the critical r–value of 0.095 at a 0.05 significance level with 1 and 334 degrees of freedom. The result is significant; therefore, the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between principals’ perseverance and their administrative task performance is rejected in favour of the alternative one. The result means that, there is a significant relationship between principals’ perseverance and their administrative task performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District (Eket Senatorial District) of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

Principals’ Self Confidence and Their Administrative Effectiveness.

The result of this study confirms that there is significant relationship between principals’ self-confidence and their administrative task performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District (Eket Senatorial District) of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

This finding agrees with the study of Judge, Bono, Ilies, and Gerhardt, (2002) which emphasized that in the ten existing reviews of research on leadership traits, self-confidence was the only trait that appeared in a majority (eight) of the lists. Self-confidence plays a role in every aspect of a leader's thoughts, feelings, behaviour, relationships and job performance, through an internal psychological mechanism called self-leadership.

Administrative Assistant Resource (2014) opines that for most people, their biggest obstacle is themselves. Negative thinking, low self-esteem and irrational fears are all manifestations of low self-confidence. All these factors can come in the way and can prevent an administrator from achieving success and fulfillment in his professional life. With hesitation and low self-esteem, a principal will not be able to finish work on time and this can hurt his productivity and efficiency. An administrative professional has to deal with a wide range of problems and responsibilities throughout the day. With improved self-confidence, he can finish all tasks efficiently giving more time to spend with family and on himself.

Self-confident people are able to achieve more success as they are obviously more confident, they do not overthink every small decision and they don't get into situations expecting to fail. People who lack self-confidence set themselves up for failure because they expect to fail even before they even start off with any project. As an administrative professional, the stresses of the job and the constant need to multitask can get you down. With improved self-confidence, you will be prepared to take on and tackle more responsibilities, have an optimistic view, and be able to handle bad situations in a much better and more diplomatic way.

Principals' Perseverance and Their Administrative Task Performance.

The finding of this study shows a significant relationship between principals' perseverance and their administrative task performance in public secondary schools in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District (Eket Senatorial District) of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria.

This finding is supported by the work of Brian Dodd (2018) who opined that the benefits of perseverance are: i. driving you back to those who love you unconditionally. ii. Reminding you of who to put your trust in. iii. Reminding

you of how much a man's applause still matters to you. iv. Reminding you of your calling. v. Reminding you of life's uncertainty. vi. Perseverance makes you humble. vii. Perseverance reminds you of the importance of building a quality team around you. viii. Perseverance is fuelled by optimism and hope. ix. Perseverance eventually finishes its work.

Lathan (2021) states that the best principals are willing to commit to a school and persevere despite obstacles or challenges. After all, realizing a vision doesn't happen overnight; true transformation takes time. A leader's commitment displays not only passion but dedication, which can have a tremendously positive effect on school culture. According to Richard Ingersoll (2001), the level of administrative support in a school is a major factor in whether teachers decide to persevere in their profession.

5 Conclusion and Recommendation

Considering the findings of this study, it is obvious that principals' leadership traits of self-confidence and perseverance significantly relate to their administrative task performance in Akwa Ibom South Senatorial District (Eket Senatorial District) of Akwa Ibom State. The following recommendations are made:

1. Principals of schools should be confident in themselves at all times. The spirit of self-confidence will enable a school principal to pursue the goals/ objectives of the school with a determination to attain them. A confident principal inculcates the spirit of self-confidence in his followers thereby leading to the attainment of school objectives.
2. School principals should develop the spirit of perseverance at all times. This is the only way that they will be able to face the challenges and obstacles they may come in contact with in the pursuit of the administrative duties. They must learn to accept failures but never to give up on their goals even if they fail severally. It is often said that "the fall of a man is not the end of his life."

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